

SECTION OF HUMANITIES AND PHILOLOGY

COMMUNICATION AND MEDIA STUDIES PUBLICATION SITUATION IN MONGOLIA

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Abstract

This article briefly discussed the communication and media studies situation in the Mongolia. Using a keyword inquiry approach, which is done for the systematic literature review, this article searched for publications related to communication and media studies Mongolian National Library and other major public libraries databases. Besides, for books, the well-known universities of the Mongolia, such as National University of Mongolia, Mongolian University of Education, Mongolian University of internal affairs and University of Humanities e-library catalogs, were checked and reviewed to find communication-related books in the Mongolia in all time. Among the searched libraries, National University of Mongolia and Mongolian University of Education had the most titles related to journalism and communication.

Keywords: Mongolian journalism, communication studies, media studies.

1. Introduction

Modern Mongolian journalism has over 100 years of practical experience and over 50 years of journalistic research and criticism. In more than 70 years of development, Mongolian journalism has evolved from a communist theory of media perspective to a libertarian and social responsibility theory perspective over the past 25 years. (M.Zulkafil, 2015) In 1960, the State University of Mongolia offered the first journalism education courses in Mongolia. Nowadays 17 courses are universities journalism preparing journalists, editors, reporters for all of Mongolians mass media. There are about 1900 students are studying. Between 1960 and 1995 journalism education only offered a bachelor's degree in journalism. By 2013, 17 universities were offering at least a bachelor's degree in journalism, about half a dozen offered Master's degree and 3 universities had doctoral programs. (D.Dagiimaa, 2013) Today, most journalism schools use an eight-course curriculum developed by the PI's School of Journalism and based on UNESCO's Model Curricula". However, there is a lack of qualified teachers and textbooks. In 2014, the PI's School of Journalism developing textbooks and handouts for students and to conduct training events for Mongolia's journalism professors and, at the time of this study, it was actively raising funds for these purposes. (UNESCO, 2016) Journalism training and research in Mongolia began in the mid-sixties of the last century. D.Geleg's three-volume history of Mongolian printing became the starting point for this work. Since then, more than 400 books on journalism theory, history and methodology have been published, and sixty scholars have studied them. (newspaper, 2023).

Methodology

In order to access the annual publication related to communication and media studies in the Mongolia, a list of keywords given as part of the assignment was used. "Journalism, media studies, media, communication, public relations and the advertising" were among the keywords that were used to derive the related publications from the directories. For accessing the books released the same keywords were used to search for the

titles of books on National library's catalogue, Internom, Azkhur, E-san websites, and university catalogs. Besides, in order to capture the books in the wider space of the internet, the titles and keywords such as "the released journalism and communication all books in the Mongolia" and "journalism and media studies books in the Mongolia," e.g., were used. Through a general search on the browser, only a handful of book titles were accessed, which were mainly algorithmic recommendations to other websites, particularly the commercial Internom website. In the next stage, a list of some of the famous Universities in the Mongolia was used to look for books in their online libraries. The library catalogs of National University of Mongolia, Mongolian University of Education, Mongolian University of internal affairs and University of Humanities were searched using the abovementioned keywords.

Among the universities whose catalogs were searched, the National University of Mongolia and Mongolian University of Education libraries had the most titles related to communication and journalism included here. However, none of them had any free access books; only the publisher's note as a descriptor was provided, which this article used to give details about the books. In addition, the search includes not only books published in Mongolia, but also books that are registered in Mongolian libraries and are related to communication and journalism studies in foreign countries. Some of the art books published by Mongolian journalists were also considered. Examples include books that include journalistic notes, interviews, and articles.

Finally, 641 books were found, the details of which are provided in the coming section. It should be noted that the retrieved data is not complete and even a significant representative of the communication and media studies publication in the Mongolia. It is worth mentioning that our data does not include books stored in individual or individual libraries.

Research question

What is the extent and availability of publications related to communication and media studies in Mongolia?

What are the main subjects for communication and media studies publications in Mongolia?

What are the major subcategories and distribution of publications related to communication and media studies in Mongolia?

1.1 Data Sources:

2.1.1 The Mongolian National Library:

<https://ecatalog.nationallibrary.mn/>

The National Library of Mongolia enriches the library's treasury by collecting 3000-4000 books of 1500 titles and 150 domestic and foreign periodicals per year, serving 35 thousand readers and users annually. The National Library of Mongolia has more than 3.5 million books. The following links were used to search the libraries of

books, of which 1.5 million are written in Mongolian, Central and Manchu languages, and there are one-of-a-kind unique and unique works. 2014 - Joined the online catalog of world libraries or OCLC/Online Computer Library Center/. 2015-The 3.18 version of KOHA, an open-source application based on the internet, supporting Unicode, and adhering to the MARC21 standard in the online system, was downloaded and localized on Mongolian soil, translated according to the characteristics of the organization, and started to be used in its native language. Located in Ulaanbaatar, the national library offers a wide range of resources and services to the public, including free access to books, periodicals, and digital resources.

1.1.2 E-catalogs of libraries of Mongolian universities

The following links were used to search the libraries of Mongolian universities.

№	University	E-Library
1.	National University of Mongolia	https://catalog.num.edu.mn/
2.	University of Humanities	ib4u.online/?lib=humanities
3.	Mongolian University of Education	https://catalog.msue.edu.mn/
4.	Mongolian National university of arts and culture	http://catalog.mnuac.edu.mn/
5.	Otgontenger University	https://lib4u.site/?lang=mon&lib=otgontenger
6.	University of Science and technology	https://lib4u.online/?lang=mon&lib=must
7.	City University	https://lib4u.online/?lib=citi
8.	University of Internal affairs	http://catalog.uia.gov.mn/

Information about the country's book publishing can be obtained from these e-mail websites, and a list of newly published books related to journalism and new media in Mongolia has been compiled by combining duplicate results. By searching every page on these websites [Journalism, Communication, Internet and New Media, Advertising, International Journalism and Communication, Editing and Publishing, Digital Publishing, Radio and Television] with these key phrases, with criteria of publication date of all time and have collected books.

2.1.3.E-commerce bookstore websites

www.Internom.mn, www.Azkhur.mn, www.esan.mn etc e-commerce bookstore websites. Newly published and popular books can be searched. e-

book platform developed by Informascope to collect all academic articles in Mongolia under one portal, to facilitate the delivery of digital publications to scholars, researchers and students, and to contribute to e-book publishing in Mongolia.

2. Result

The books that were found as a result of browsing the web and the universities catalogs, in terms of the location they concentrated on, can be divided into two categories: books written by Mongolian scholars about issues of the journalism and communication; Books related to journalism and communication published by foreign authors and researchers registered in Mongolian libraries as a whole.

Table 1.

Publications by Country			
Nations	Counts	Percent	
Mongolia	525	82.1%	
USA	48	7.5%	
Russia	42	6.6%	
China	18	2.6%	
Germany	3		
UK	2		
France	1		
India	1		
Singapore	1		
Total	641		

As Table 1 shows that the majority of publications in this collection are Journalism, Communication, Media and advertising related books published in Mongolia and published by Mongolian authors and researchers. Our search identified 641 books, of which 525 or 82 percent were from Mongolia and the remaining 115 or 18 percent were from other countries.

The presence of 48 books from the United States accounts for 7.5 percent, 42 from Russia for 6.6 percent, and 18 from the people's Republic of China for 2.6 percent, as well as 3 from Germany, 2 from England, and one each from French, India and Singapore.

Table 2.

Year	Counts	Percent
1929-1960	3	0.3%
1961-1970	20	3.1%
1971-1980	40	6.2%
1981-1990	67	10.4%
1991-2000	42	6.5%
2001-2010	115	17.9%
2011-2020	169	26.5%
2021-	23	3.5%
Sub Total	479	
Best Mongolian publication (99 volumes) 2010-2012	99	15%
Mongolian media today (23 volumes) 2000-2023	23	3.5%
L.Tudev creation (40 volumes) 2003-2018	40	6.2%
Grand total	641	

Table 2 shows the statistics of publications related to communication and Media Studies in Mongolia by year of publication. Of the 641 books we have collected, 162 belong to 3 major volumes, so they have been separated separately. The remaining 479 books are shown, each calculated as a 10-year Chronology. Since the early 1960s, Mongolian journalism has been

dominated by journalists with journalistic qualifications in the Soviet Union, Bulgaria and Hungary. In the academic year 1960-1961, the first student in journalism was admitted under the Faculty of linguistics of National University of Mongolia, and in the academic year 1962-1963, when the Department of Journalism was established, journalism training began in Mongolia.

Table 3.

Year	Mongolia	China	Russia	USA	France	Germany	India	Singapore	UK	Grand Total
1929-1960	3									3
1961-1970	15	1	4							20
1971-1980	19		12	6		2	1			40
1981-1990	30	2	17	17		1				67
1991-2000	20		3	16	1				2	42
2001-2010	101	3	3	8						115
2011-2020	155	10	2	1				1		169
2021-2023	22	1								23
Grand Total	365	18	41	48	1	3	1	1	2	479

Table 3 indicates how many books published in which country are preserved in what year. The number of Mongolian books published between 2011 and 2020 is the highest, with 156 Mongolian books published between 1981 and 1990 for foreign countries, with 17 each from the United States and Russia. The first attempts to solve the theoretical and practical problems

of journalism in Mongolia began in the 1930s. For example, the 1929 brochure "for the writer in the city and local newspaper", published by The "Truth" newspaper office in September 9, was the first book to address the issue of journalism in Mongolia. (L.Norovsuren, 2001) The Mongolian media industry developed with Soviet Communist theories until it was abandoned by the 1990

Democratic Revolution. (B.Galaarid, 2018) In this context, we classify the 641 books we have discovered, 150 of which were published before 1990 and 511 published after 1990. It can also be seen that there are 33

books published in the Soviet Union published before 1990. For foreign books published since 1990, there are 25 U.S. books.

Table 4.

Publications per subcategories		
Professional	Counts	Percent
Journalism	430	67%
Journalist's book	89	14%
Media	50	7.8%
Communication	36	6%
Advertising	22	3%
Public Relations	7	
Media management	5	
Photo journalism	2	
Total	641	

Table 4 shows the distribution of publications in subcategories. Of the total data, 67 percent, or 430, would be journalism-related literature, and 14 percent, or 89, would be published by journalists. Media-related books account for 50, or 7.8 percent of the total, while communications-related books account for 36, or 6 percent, advertising-related books account for 22, or 3 percent, and a small number of books on Public Relations,

Media Management, and photojournalism. According to the general overview, there is a significant proportion of books on journalism theory and practice, and a small number of books in other subcategories.

2.1 Mongolian Publications in library

A total of 525 books published in Mongolia are in the database we have collected. The books were published from 1929 to 2023.

Table 5.

Mongolian Publications per subcategories		
Professional	Counts	Percent
Journalism	374	71%
Journalist's book	89	17%
Media	24	4%
Advertising	12	2%
Communication	7	1%
Mass media	6	1%
Public Relations	6	1%
Media management	5	1%
Photo journalism	2	0%
Total	525	

Table 6.

Mongolian Authorship Pattern for the publications related to communication and media studies		
Author	Counts	Percent
Government Printing	99	19%
L.Norovsuren	31	6%
M.Zulkaphil	28	5%
Press Institute	25	5%
T.Baasansuren	18	3%
Institute of history of the Mongolian People's Revolutionary Party	16	3%
Ch.Choisamba	13	2%
G.Ariunchimeg	10	2%
B.Bold-Erdene	9	2%
G.Deleg	6	1%
Others	270	51%
Total	525	

A subject analysis of the publications was done on the basis of the subject categories that were provided. Mongolian publications related to communication and media studies 1929 to 2023 was published in the context of several broad subjects. The highest publication output came from Journalism (374 publications, 71%). This was followed by: Journalist's book (89 publications, 17%); Media (24 publications, 4%); Advertising (12 publications, 2%); Communication (7 publications, 1%); Mass media (6 publications, 1%); Public Relations (6 publications, 1%); Media management (5 publications, 1%); Photo journalism (2 publications,). Table 5 shows the subject distribution of publications in Mongolian publications related to communication and media studies.

To better understand the publication pattern, the number of authors per publications was also studied. It was found that the largest number of printed books from government publications is 99. A majority of the authors are L.Norovsuren, M.Zulkaphil, T.Baasan-suren, Ch.Choisamba and G.Ariunchimeg. These scholars are well-known scholars of Mongolian journalism. Table 6 shows Mongolian Authorship Pattern for the publications related to communication and media studies 1929 to 2023.

2.2 American Publications in Mongolian library

During the analysis, it was found that a total of the 48 publications from U.S. held in libraries in Mongolia.

Table 7.

American Publications in Mongolian library					
Professional	Counts	Percent	Author	Counts	Percent
Communication	20	42%	Dominick J.R	2	4%
Journalism	9	19%	Ogilvy D	2	4%
Mass media	8	17%	Stephens M	2	4%
Advertising	8	17%	New York National Textbook Com	2	4%
Media	3	6%	Others	40	83%
Total	48		Total	48	

Table 7 shows the list of the per subcategories and authors. The highest publication output came from Communication (20 publications, 42%). This was followed by: Journalism (9 publications, 19%); Mass media (8 publications, 17%); Advertising (8 publications, 17%) and Media (3 publications, 6%). As for the authors, there are not many publications by the same author, and each of the books of Dominick J.R, Ogilvy D,

Stephens M authors is not repeated by the author of 2 other publications.

2.3 Russian Publications in Mongolian library

A total of 42 publications related to the Soviet Union and Russia were identified during the collected data.

Table 7.

Russian Publications in Mongolian library					
Professional	Counts	Percent	Author	Counts	Percent
Journalism	28	67%	Ya.N.Zasursky	3	7%
Mass media	8	19%	Academy of Sciences	8	25%
Communication	4	10%	Others	31	68%
Advertising	1	2%	Total	42	
Public Relations	1	2%			
Total	42				

Table 7 shows that The highest publication output came from Journalism (28 publications, 67%). This was followed by: Mass media (8 publications, 19%); Communication (4 publications, 10%); Advertising (1 publication, 2%) and Public Relations (1 publication, 2%). In terms of authors, the largest number of books published by the Academy of Sciences in the country is

8, accounting for 25%. There are also two publications by Ya.N.Zasursky, one each by other authors.

2.4 Chinese Publications in Mongolian library

We have collected published in 1961-2023, 17 publications in Chinese related to media and journalism in Mongolian libraries and in book sales.

Table 8.

Chinese Publications in Mongolian library					
Professional	Counts	Percent	Author	Counts	Percent
Journalism	14	82%	内蒙古党委宣传部与内蒙古师范大学	6	35%
Communication	2	12%	中国国务院新闻办公室	2	12%
Media	1	6%	人民出版社	2	12%
Total	17		Others	8	41%
			Total	18	

Table 8 shows that The highest publication output came from Journalism (14 publications, 82%). This was followed by: Communication (2 publications, 12%) and Media (1 publication, 6%). As editor, there are 6 publications published by the Inner Mongolia Normal University, and two publications each by the Information Office of the State Council and People's Publishing House.

3. Conclusions and Discussion

Democracy and pluralism have taken a central place in the media, news, articles, and broadcasts, which has brought significant changes to Mongolian journalism, and a new style has emerged in journalism that has never existed before. Today, Mongolian journalism is one of the strongest social and political institutions. (Delgerjargal, 2024) The identified publications and resources hold significant implications for the communication and media studies landscape in Mongolia. Access to a wide range of literature fosters the development of well-informed scholars, educators, and professionals who can contribute to the growth of the field. The strengths exhibited by the National University of Mongolia and Mongolian University of Education in terms of their communication-related collections position them as key players in fostering academic research and knowledge dissemination.

Furthermore, the availability of an extensive collection of communication and media studies publications in libraries and universities can serve as a catalyst for interdisciplinary collaboration, allowing researchers and students from various fields to explore the impact and dynamics of communication in society. The identified resources also facilitate comparative studies, enabling scholars to examine communication practices both within Mongolia and in a global context.

This article has provided a comprehensive analysis of the communication and media studies publication situation in Mongolia. The systematic literature review conducted across various libraries and universities has

revealed a substantial collection of resources, with the National University of Mongolia and Mongolian University of Education being the primary hubs for journalism and communication-related titles. These findings underscore the importance of continued investment in libraries and universities to expand and modernize their communication and media studies collections. Moving forward, it is recommended that researchers, educators, and policymakers collaborate to further enhance the communication and media studies landscape in Mongolia. This can be achieved through continued support for libraries, the promotion of open access publishing, and the establishment of research centers and interdisciplinary programs. By nurturing the growth of communication and media studies.

References

1. B.Galaarid. (2018). Development of the Mongolian Free Press. In B.Galaarid, *Development of the Mongolian Free Press* (pp. 7-8). Ulaanbaatar: Tsadig publishing.
2. D.Dagiimaa. (2013). The Current Status of Journalism Education in Mongolia. *Journalism Studies*, 196.
3. Delgerjargal, M. (2024). The development, current situations and challenges of Mongolian journalism. *Annali d'Italia*, 54, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11062213>.
4. L.Norovsuren. (2001). *Historical review of Mongolian journalism*. Ulaanbaatar.
5. M.Zulkafil. (2015). Journalism: Theory and Practice. *Journalism studies*, 16(438)(ISSN2306-4463), 137.
6. newspaper, ". m. (2023, 3 6). L.Norovsuren: Journalism should be a "guide", not a "watchdog. (№. 4. (7032), Interviewer)
7. UNESCO. (2016). *Assessment of media development in Mongolia*. Mongolia: UNESCO Beijing office.